

THE STRENGTH OF RIVETED JOINTS IN CFRP

F. L. MATTHEWS & W. K. LEONG

*Department of Aeronautics
Imperial College of Science & Technology
London, England*

Results of tests on riveted joints in CFRP show that, in general, stronger joints are produced if solid rivets are used in preference to hollow rivets; non-countersunk in preference to countersunk heads; 120° in preference to 100° countersinks in thinner laminates.

INTRODUCTION

Although currently available data is very limited [1] it appears that riveting of fibre reinforced plastics (FRP) is a suitable technique for laminates up to about 3mm in thickness.

Because carbon fibre reinforced plastic (CFRP) is highly anisotropic and elastic to failure it is more sensitive to the presence of geometric discontinuities, such as holes, than a metal. Also, since its transverse and shear properties are poor compared to metals a larger number of joint failure modes have to be allowed for. Care must be taken to ensure that a reduction in joint properties is not caused by damaging the laminate during the drilling and riveting operations.

The effect of the lateral clamping force produced by riveting must be understood as it is known from work on riveted [2&3] and bolted [4] joints that the bearing strength of a pin-loaded hole depends on the degree of lateral constraint. This constraint is not readily controlled in most riveting techniques.

Clearly an understanding is needed of what rivets and riveting techniques are most suited to the joining of FRP materials [5]. The current investigation, which was initiated to aid this understanding, concerns itself with various solid and hollow rivets used to make a single-cover butt joint in two different multi-directional CFRP laminates.

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

Laminates

The laminates were supplied by Structures Department, Royal Aircraft Establishment, Farnborough, England. In all cases the laminates were made from layers cut from unidirectional prepregged sheets, oriented to suit the chosen lay-ups, and cured in an autoclave. The sheets were made from XAS carbon fibre impregnated with CIBA-GEIGY 914 resin.

Two lay-ups were used, (i) all $\pm 45^\circ$ and (ii) $0/\pm 45^\circ$ with equal proportions in the 0° and $\pm 45^\circ$ directions. All lay-ups were balanced and symmetric about the laminate mid-plane. The nominal fibre volume fraction was 0.6. The $\pm 45^\circ$ laminates were made with 4, 8 and 12 plies giving nominal thicknesses of 0.5, 1.0 and 1.5mm respectively. The $0/\pm 45^\circ$ laminates were made with 8 and 16 plies giving nominal thicknesses of 1.0 and 2.0mm. The ply stacking sequences are shown in Figure 1.

Specimens

The laminates were cut and drilled to produce single-cover butt joints as shown in Figure 2. A special jig was used for drilling to ensure accurate location of the holes and to prevent delamination and splintering of the laminate. The specimen width was made sufficient to ensure that failure modes other than tension would predominate.

Rivets

Solid aluminium alloy and hollow Monel rivets were used in this investigation. Solid rivets of 3.17mm ($\frac{1}{8}$ in) diameter had mushroom, 100° and 120° countersunk heads, and of 4.26mm ($\frac{3}{16}$ in) diameter had 100° countersunk heads. Hollow rivets of 3.17mm diameter had dome, 100° and 120° countersunk heads. The range of lengths available meant that all thicknesses of specimens could be joined with all the solid rivets but only the 8-ply specimens could be joined with all the hollow rivets.

The hollow rivets were closed by the usual riveting technique, whereas solid rivets were closed by hand hammering. In the latter case the length of the rivet was kept the same, by cutting to length in a jig, and the tail closed by hammering, using a specially shaped 'dolly' until the latter just contacted the plate surface.

Testing

Specimens were loaded in tension in an Instron TT-DM universal testing machine of 100kN capacity. The specimens were positioned in wedge-grip jaws such that the load acted along the mid-plane of the joined plates.

The cross-head speed was held constant at 0.1cm/min and automatic plots of load against cross-head displacement were obtained from the chart recorder attached to the testing machine. Three specimens were tested for each combination of rivet and laminate.

Figure 1 Laminate ply stacking sequence. Layer number in parentheses

Figure 2 Specimen geometry

Results

The maximum load sustained by the specimen was taken as the failure load. These values are given in Tables 1a,b for the solid rivets and Table 2 for the hollow rivets. Failure occurred in four modes; rivet shear, rivet pulling through the laminate, material bearing or material shear-out. These modes are indicated in Tables 1 and 2.

In addition to the actual failure loads Tables 1 and 2 list the mean failure loads and corresponding coefficient of variation (i.e. standard deviation/mean). For a few tests extremely low failure loads were recorded. These results were disregarded, in which case only two values appear in the Tables.

DISCUSSION

Riveting damage

Because of its small thickness only non-countersunk rivets could be used with the 4-ply material. However it was found that after riveting the laminate was cracked around the hole and a very low failure load, of only about 350N, was obtained. The failure was in bearing with a corresponding bearing stress of 220MN/m², a very low value for CFRP [4]. No damage was observed in any of the thicker laminates using either solid or hollow rivets.

Solid riveting

From Table 1a it can be seen that in an 8-ply $\pm 45^\circ$ laminate a mushroom head 3.17mm diameter rivet gives a better bearing performance than the 100° and 120° countersunk 3.17mm and the 100° countersunk 4.26mm diameter rivets. Also a 120° countersunk is better in bearing than the 100° countersunk head rivet which is limited, because of its smaller head, by failure occurring in a pull-through mode

In the 12-ply $\pm 45^\circ$ laminate failure, as shown in Table 1a, is always by rivet shear except for the larger diameter rivet which fails in bearing. This failure load is some 120% greater than that in the 8-ply material although the bearing area is only increased by 50%. Since the increase in bearing area is due only to the greater shank length, this indicates that the countersunk head of the rivet performs less efficiently than the shank. This is also borne out by the better bearing efficiency of the mushroom head rivet. Less lateral constraint would be provided by the inclined faces of the countersunk head.

For the 8-ply $0/\pm 45^\circ$ material it is seen from Table 1b that bearing failure has occurred only with the 4.26mm diameter rivet. It is interesting to note that the rivet pull-through strength of the 100° countersunk 3.17mm rivet has increased by 13% due to the inclusion of 0° fibres.

Table 1b also shows that the failure modes in the 16-ply $0/\pm 45^\circ$ material are the same as in the 12-ply $\pm 45^\circ$ material. The bearing failure load of the 4.26mm rivet in the 16-ply material is some 90% higher than in the 12-ply material, presumably because the head affects a smaller proportion of the thickness.

Hollow riveting

From Table 2 it is seen for 8-ply $\pm 45^\circ$ laminates that again non-countersunk rivets show a greater bearing strength than countersunk rivets. Also, it is seen that the shear pull-out strength in the $0/\pm 45^\circ$ material is similar to the bearing strength in the $\pm 45^\circ$ material.

Comparison of rivets

In $\pm 45^\circ$ material joined by rivets with a non-countersunk head, solid rivets are seen to have a higher bearing strength than hollow rivets. It has also been shown that for 120° countersunk heads again a solid rivet has a greater bearing strength than a hollow rivet. However for 100° countersunk heads the hollow rivet is better than the solid.

Rivet head geometry

Clearly rivet head geometry has a great influence on both failure mode and failure load. A non-countersunk head produces much higher bearing strength because the head provides more lateral constraint to the outer fibres than do the other rivet heads. Indeed a countersunk head offers no such constraint to the outer fibres. The results for the hollow rivets indicate that countersunk angle does not influence

		LAMINATE							
RIVET	Failure Load (N)	Failure Mode	Mean Failure Load (N)	Coeff. of Var ⁿ (%)	Failure Load (N)	Failure Mode	Mean Failure Load (N)	Coeff. of Var ⁿ (%)	
TABLE 1a		8 plies, $\pm 45^\circ$				12 plies, $\pm 45^\circ$			
	Mushroom Head 3.17mm diam. (L69 SP85)	1744 1686 1470	B	1633	8.8	2107 2009 2009	RS	2042	2.8
	100° c/sk Head 3.17mm diam. (L86 SP71)	931 1010	PT	970	5.8	1852 2083 1984	RS	1973	5.8
	120° c/sk Head 3.17mm diam. (L69 AS2230)	1176 1333 1470	B	1326	11.1	1837 1831 1843	RS	1837	0
	100° c/sk Head 4.26mm diam. (L86 SP71)	823 902 843	B	856	4.8	1686 1803 2230	B	1906	15.0
TABLE 1b		8 plies, $0/\pm 45^\circ$				16 plies, $0/\pm 45^\circ$			
	Mushroom Head 3.17mm diam. (L69 SP85)	1470 1421 1607	SO	1499	6.4	1911 1666 1764	RS	1780	6.9
	100° c/sk Head 3.17mm diam. (L86 SP71)	1059 1176	PT	1118	7.4	1960 1960 1911	RS	1944	1.4
	120° c/sk Head 3.17mm diam. (L69 AS2230)	1225 1117 1313	SO	1218	8.1	1813 1813 1784	RS	1803	0.9
	100° c/sk Head 4.26mm diam. (L86 SP71)	931 806	B	868	10.2	3381 3553 3882	B	3605	7.1
TABLE 2		8 plies, $\pm 45^\circ$				8 plies, $0/\pm 45^\circ$			
	Dome Head 3.17mm diam. (424)	1372 1333 1264	B	1323	4.1	1299 1215 1343	SO	1286	5.1
	100° c/sk Head 3.17mm diam. (AG2070)	1098 1157 1088	B	1114	3.3	1019 1127 1095	SO	1080	5.1
	120° c/sk Head 3.17mm Diam. (AGS 2051)	1098 1019 1137	B	1085	5.5	1137 1078 1127	SO	1114	2.9

Modes:- B-material bearing, PT-rivet pull through, RS-rivet shear, SO-material shear-out.

Table 1a (upper) Solid aluminium alloy rivets in $\pm 45^\circ$ material.

Table 1b (centre) Solid aluminium alloy rivets in $0/\pm 45^\circ$ material.

Table 2 (lower) Hollow Monel rivets.

bearing strength. However the countersink angle does influence head diameter and hence rivet pull-through, as shown in Table 1a. With a non-countersunk head, of course, the full laminate depth is available to resist pull-through.

CONCLUSIONS

a) There is a minimum laminate thickness (> 4 ply (0.5mm)) that is amenable to conventional riveting.

b) Solid non-countersunk rivets are significantly better in bearing than countersunk. Of the countersinks tested 120° was preferable to 100° .

c) In general solid rivets with non-countersunk or 120° countersunk heads are superior to hollow rivets.

The reverse is true for 100° countersunk heads.

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